

Optimal Location of Normally Closed Switches in Medium Voltage Distribution Networks

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Abstract—This research paper presents a deterministic optimization technique for the optimal location of normally closed switches on a realistic medium voltage distribution network located in Portugal. The goal is to minimize the expected outage costs to consumers in conjunction with normally closed switches capital investment, installation, and annual operation and maintenance costs, improving at the same time the level of reliability and service quality of distribution networks. The optimization approach is developed as mixed-integer linear programming using CPLEX solver in the TOMLAB optimization tool. The global solution obtained was successfully tested and validated with real data of the above-mentioned Portuguese network. The presented results indicate the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Index Terms—Distribution networks, Mixed integer linear programming, Normally closed switch placement, Reliability.

NOMENCLATURE

$ECOST$	Expected outage cost to customers
NF	Total number of possible fault locations
NL	Total number of load points
$\lambda(i)$	Average failure rate of possible fault location i
$C^{dij}(i, j)$	Customer damage function
$L(j)$	Average load of the customer located at the j th load point
NC	Total number of NC switches installed in network
INV	Total cost of NC switches installed in network
CRF	Capital recovery factor
dr	Discount rate

t	Project lifetime
N_f	Total number of feeders
$X(NC, f)$	Binary decision variable which is equal to 1 if a NC switch is installed on the NC th location of feeder f
$C^{dij}(i, j, f)$	Customer damage function
N	Total number of available NC switches
$C^{dij^{Switching}}(i, j, f)$	Customer damage function value for the outage duration equal to switching time
$C^{dij^{Repair}}(i, j, f)$	Customer damage function value for the outage duration equal to the i th fault clearance time

I. INTRODUCTION

An electric power system is expected to provide electricity as economically as possible while ensuring a high degree of continuity and quality of service [1, 2]. It is extremely important to provide electric energy with security and guarantee since electricity delivery has an essential service. The electric power distribution system aims to deliver electricity to the final customers of the whole electric supply chain. Thus, due to the complexity of actual distribution systems, their analysis and planning are of major importance.

Usually, medium voltage (MV) distribution networks are meshed in design but operated radially. In distribution networks, two types of switches can be found, normally open (NO) and normally closed (NC), and it is the switching of these devices that allows the radial operation of the distribution networks [3]. The selection of the optimal number of switches and their locations is an optimization problem that requires cost/benefit analysis to justify the investment costs [4].

The distribution system switching placement problem is a complex, combinatorial, and constrained optimization problem [5, 6]. Heuristic methods are widely used in literature to solve the optimal switches location. A procedure based on a genetic algorithm is presented in [7] to define the number and placement of NO and NC switches and if they should or not be remote-controlled switch (RCS) devices. The genetic algorithm uses two indices to evaluate network reliability: the system average interruption duration index (SAIDI) and Energy Not Supplied (ENS). The proposed genetic algorithm was evaluated with ten real distribution feeders from a large-scale network. Decomposition and convex analysis techniques are used in [8] to determine the optimal number of NC switches and their optimal location to maximize the tradeoff between ENS costs and investment costs. This work presents a polynomial-time algorithm for space partitioning into independent subspaces and a convex optimization algorithm to solve the optimization problem in each subspace. The proposed approach is illustrated with an example from a real urban distribution network.

The techniques mentioned above, i.e., heuristic algorithms, explore only a narrow region of the search space and tend to get stuck into a locally optimal solution. On the other hand, unlike heuristics, deterministic methods such as linear programming and mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) have proven to reach the global optimum solution in a finite number of steps [4].

A methodology to find the NC switches optimal location in a MV distribution network is presented in [9]. The methodology allows locating the switches in a given electrical network to ensure the minimum ENS. The methodology is based upon the consecutive installation of two switches in every feeder. All the possible location pairs are generated. The methodology considers the previously existing NO and NC switches as well as the independent generation sources already connected to the MV electrical network. A deterministic methodology for distribution networks reconfiguration is proposed in [3], aiming the minimization of active power losses. The proposed reconfiguration method is based on an optimal power flow supported by the DC model. The goal is to find the optimal radial topology through the optimal location of NO switches. The method was formulated as a mixed-integer quadratic problem (MIQP). The Joule effect gives the power losses, calculated according to each distribution line. A new optimization approach for distribution automation in terms of automated and remotely controlled sectionalizing switch placement is introduced in [4]. It is introduced a MILP formulation and investigates the importance of the customer types and load density in determining the sectionalizing switch placement strategy. The proposed model was successfully tested on bus 4 of the Roy Billinton Test System (RBTS) and a real-size case study.

The present research paper proposes a deterministic technique for the NC switches optimal location. Based on the radial topology of the distribution network presented in [3] through the optimal location of NO switches, the main contributions of this work are the following:

- Introduce a MILP formulation to evaluate the network's reliability;

- Consider the customer outage costs as well as NC switch investment, operation, and maintenance cost, through the optimal location of NC switches;
- Propose a distribution network with minimal losses and maximum reliability.

This research paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the proposed methodology after this introduction. The case study to show the application of the proposed methodology, as well as the results and its discussion, are shown in Section 3. Finally, Section 4 presents the most relevant conclusions.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The distribution network's reliability implies providing electric energy to customers without interruption in service delivery. It is estimated that about 70% of the total interruption time of the power system is associated with permanent faults [7]. Therefore, the benefits of allocated NC switches can be quantified in terms of the outage duration reduction and the number of customers affected during the permanent faults by fast restoring power to those not affected. This can be done by switching NC switches.

The proposed method is based on the technique proposed in [4] and on the radial topology of the distribution network obtained in [3].

To quantify the customer outage costs, the expected outage cost to customers (ECOST) index is the best way. This index affects the system topology, interruption durations, load variations, equipment failure probability, and the customer damage function. Equation (1) shows how to calculate ECOST for a typical feeder:

$$ECOST = \sum_{i=1}^{NF} \sum_{j=1}^{NL} \lambda(i) \times C^{dij}(i, j) \times L(j) \quad (1)$$

In this research paper, a fault is defined as the occurrence of a permanent fault on a feeder section or transformer or the occurrence of a sustained interruption due to a failure of any component of the system. The present methodology considers that each feeder's starting and ending point is connected to NC and NO circuit breakers (CBs). The switching actions occur after a fault as follows:

1. The NC CB operates and de-energizes all of the downstream load points;
2. The faulty area is isolated by opening the adjacent upstream and downstream NC switches if any NC switches exist;
3. The NO and NC CBs are closed in order to restore power to as many disrupted customers as possible.

The costs of NC switches can be quantified by equation (2) in terms of NC switch capital investment (CI), installation cost (IC), and annual operation and maintenance cost (MC):

$$INV = \sum_{NC=1}^{N_{NC}} CI(NC) + IC(NC) + MC(NC) \quad (2)$$

To have an economic evaluation considering a time horizon for the investments, the proposed method considers the capital recovery factor (CRF). The equation (3) defines the CRF mathematically [10, 11]:

$$CRF = \frac{dr \times (1 + dr)^t}{(1 + dr)^t - 1} \quad (3)$$

where dr is the discount rate and t is the project lifetime.

The NC switch placement problem in distribution networks can be formulated by a MILP as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min} \quad & \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{F_f}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{L_f}} [\lambda(i, f) \times C^{dij}(i, j, f) \times L(j, f) \\ & \quad \times CRF^{-1}] \\ & + \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} \sum_{NC=1}^{N_{NC}} [CI(NC) + IC(NC) \\ & \quad + (MC(NC) \times CRF^{-1}) \\ & \quad + X(NC, f)] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The goal is to minimize the total system cost in terms of customer outage cost (i.e., ECOST and INV costs). The customer damage function, $C^{dij}(i, j, f)$, depends on the amount of time required to restore the customers disrupted due to each fault. The objective function (4) is subject to the following constraints:

Subject to

$$\sum_{NC=1}^{N_{NC}} X(NC, f) \leq N \quad (5)$$

$$C^{dij}(i, j, f) \geq C^{dij, \text{Switching}}(i, j, f) \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C^{dij}(i, j, f) & \geq C^{dij, \text{Repair}}(i, j, f) \\ & \times [1 - \sum_{NC=NC_i}^{NC_j} X(NC, f)] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Constraint (5) limits the number of available NC switches for installation in case of budget inadequacy. Constraints (6) and (7) restrict the customer damage function based on the number, location, and switching time of NC switches as well as CBs and also on faulted equipment repair time.

III. CASE STUDY

The main objective of this research work is to determine the optimal location of NC switches in a distribution MV network and minimize the total system cost.

The proposed method is tested in a realistic MV distribution network (15 kV) in Portugal. The network is supplied by two substations and has 220 buses, where 143 buses are load buses. The network has 21.02 MW of active load, over 59.9 km of overhead lines and underground cables. Fig. 1 shows the single line diagram of the network under study. Table I presents the main characteristics of each feeder of the network.

Fig. 1. 220 buses MV distribution network diagram.

TABLE I. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRIBUTION NETWORK.

Feeder ID	Total number of fault locations (NF)	Total number of load points (NL)	Active load (kW)	Available positions to install a NC switch
A	40	40	4,130.14	79
B	48	48	6,053.82	95
C	67	68	5,441.27	133
D	63	64	5,391.53	125
Total	218	220	21,016.76	432

This proposed research work was developed in a computer with one Intel Xeon E5-2620 v2 processor and 16 GB of RAM running Windows 10 Pro using the MATLAB R2018a and TOMLAB 8.1 64 bits with CPLEX solver (version 12.5).

A. Test Scenarios

To test and prove the proposed method, four scenarios are considered:

- Scenario 1: The ECOST of the network is calculated without any NC switch.
- Scenario 2: The goal is to find the optimal number and location of NC switches of the network depicted in Fig. 1.

- Scenario 3: In this scenario, the customer damage functions are increased from 100% to 1000% of their initial values, with steps of 50%, to evaluate the impact of customer damage function variation on the optimal NC switches number.
- Scenario 4: Study the effect of the budget inadequacy by limiting the number of available NC switches. For this, the number of available switches is increased from 0 to 10 to illustrate the effect of NC switch placement in terms of reliability and ECOST.

In this case study, the maintenance cost is ignored. Table II presents the necessary basic parameters for the implementation of the proposed model. The customer damage functions data are extracted from [12]. 0.05% of discount rate is considered for a thirty-year project lifetime, leading to 0.034 ratio of capital recovery factor (CRF).

TABLE II. BASIC PARAMETERS CONSIDERED FOR EACH SCENARIO.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unity
Project lifetime	T	30	Years
Capital Recovery Factor	CRF	0.0336	-
Total number of available positions to install a NC switch	N_{NC}	432	Positions
Capital investment and installation costs	$CI(NC) + IC(NC)$	17,000	€
Customer damage function value for the outage duration equal to switching time.	$C_{ij}^{Switching}$	0.06	€/kw
Switching time of NC switch	$T^{Switching}$	10	min
Customer damage function value for the outage duration equal to repair time	C_{ij}^{Repair}	5.00	€/kw
Fault repair time	T^{Repair}	10	hours

B. Results and Discussion

Table III compares the results obtained in Scenario 1 and Scenario 2. The results indicate that even with the costs of NC switches, the total system cost is reduced by 16%. Furthermore, as expected, the ECOST also was reduced. Therefore, the number of NC switches installed presented in Table III represents the global optimum solution for the formulated problem. Fig. 2 illustrates the optimal locations of NC switches obtained by utilizing the proposed approach for the considered distribution network.

TABLE III. RESULTS: SCENARIO 1 VS SCENARIO 2.

Scenario	Optimal Number of NC switches	ECOST (€)	Total System Cost (€)
1	0	827,414.64	827,414.64
2	4	627,287.79	695,287.79

In what concerns Scenario 3, Fig. 3 illustrates how the optimal number of NC switches increases as the customer damage function increases, indicating that a higher level of reliability is required. As can be seen from Fig. 3, there is a nonlinear increase in the number of NC switches due to the complex linkage between the customer damage function, outages duration, and the distribution network topology. To

illustrate the fact that the installation of the first NC switch has the highest impact on ECOST reduction, Fig. 4 plots the variations of the ECOST, installed NC switches cost, and the total system cost versus the customer damage function multiplier. Fig. 4 shows that the impact on reducing ECOST decreases as the number of installed NC switches increases.

Fig. 2. Optimal location of NC switches.

Fig. 3. Optimal number of NC switches installed versus the customer damage function variation.

To analyze Scenario 4, Fig. 5 illustrates the variation of ECOST, installed NC switches cost, and total system cost versus the number of available switches for installation. As can be seen, the installation of the first NC switch has the highest effect on reducing the ECOST. After the optimal number of NC switches (i.e., 4) was reached, the benefit of switch placement is less than it costs. This analysis also verifies the optimality of the solution achieved in Scenario 2.

The execution times of the proposed model are 1.35, 1.40, 20.67, and 10.09 seconds for Scenarios 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

Fig. 4. Total system cost, ECOST and NC switches cost versus the customer damage function variation.

Fig. 5. ECOST, installed NC switches cost and system total cost versus number of available NC switches for installation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a deterministic methodology modeled as a mixed integer linear programming for optimal NC switch placement in medium voltage distribution networks which considers the costs associated with consumer outages versus the NC switch capital investment, installation, as well as annual operation costs. This methodology has significant advantages since it ensures the optimal solution to the problem in almost real-time. The proposed approach was developed in TOMLAB software tool. Furthermore, a real-size case study revealed the accuracy and performance of the formulation through four different proposed Scenarios.

The optimal location of NO and NC switches in medium voltage distribution networks has major importance for planning and operation. Two of the most important goals considered in planning and operating a medium voltage distribution network are reducing power losses and increasing

grid reliability, which was successfully accomplished in the proposed method.

The method proved to be adequate to support the distribution network operator for planning future network investment.

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